

Evaluation of Slaughterhouse Infrastructure According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO) - Gezira State, Sudan

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to evaluate general and specific requirement of Gezira states slaughter house according to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization SSMO. A total of 12 local slaughterhouse of Gezira state from different sites of localities were divided into three categories according to their constructions and establishment due to data sheets that created includes ten items (1-10), each item score ten marks when SSMO was found actually for evaluating slaughterhouse site, general shape building design, accessories equipments, drainage, services and general requirements. All the data of the experiments were statistically analyzed by analyses of variance applicable to completely randomized designs CRD.ANOVA table at a confidence level of 5%. Questioner analyzed with Chi square test by using the computer with Statistical

Package for Social Study (SPSS) program and Duncan multiple range tests was used to detect difference between means. According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets the study showed no significant different ($P<0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughterhouse site for living area, waste places, industrial polluted areas, odorous areas, insect and pest areas, livestock marketing place, main roads, voltage areas and communication media while the study showed significant different ($P<0.05$) between experimental groups for slaughter house drainage system. Slaughterhouse general structures showed no significant different ($P<0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughter house surround structure while workers entrance, exits, animal entrance door preparing,

operations and waiting pens showed significant different ($P < 0.05$) between experimental groups. Slaughterhouse accessories showed no significant different ($P < 0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for maintenance workshop and animal transport traffics while the study showed significant different ($P < 0.05$) between experimental groups for slaughter house car wash unit, building foundation, slaughterhouse walls, slaughterhouse floor, slaughterhouse roofs, ventilation and light, pens design, animals partitions, water resources, and animal quarantine. The study showed all the slaughterhouse of Gezira state don't matching Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization requirements so, the authors recommend to entitling and establishing new slaughterhouses that conform to the Sudanese standard for the slaughterhouse.

Keywords: *slaughterhouse, building standards, Sudanese Standards and Metrology agency (SSMO), environmental problems.*

Introduction

More than 163 million animals, including livestock, poultry, and equines, as well as 76,000 tons of fish stock and a sizable number of wild animals, are kept in Sudan. Because most of these animals are kept by nomadic tribes on natural pastures, they are almost entirely free of feed additives, hormonal byproducts, and chemical residues, which give Sudanese animal products a special preference. As a renewable resource, the livestock industry in Sudan is vital to the country's economy and overall population welfare. MOAR (2017). The majority of these animals are used to produce meat for domestic and international export. Every individual meat trade has its own needs that improve the sanitary production of that particular sort of meat, in addition to the general requirements that are detailed in the module "Layout and construction." Abattoirs or slaughter houses have their own unique designs that allow the staff to slaughter and dress the carcass in a hygienic manner, as well as to encourage simple working circumstances that lessen stressful working situations that lead to inappropriate workplace behaviors. Maja, (2007). Consumers, meat processors, merchants, the food service sector, government organizations, academic institutions, public health specialists, researchers, and the general public locally, regionally, nationally, and internationally are all very concerned about the safety of meat. Government officials, food processors, food handlers, food suppliers, and consumers

themselves should ideally be constantly monitoring the safety of meat during slaughtering, processing, packaging, transporting, storing, exhibiting, selling, cooking, serving, and ultimately consumption. Mareel, (2001). A slaughterhouse, as defined by legislation, is a facility used for killing and dressing animals whose flesh is meant for human consumption. (García, et.al., 2023). An establishment that deals with the killing and preparation of meat animals for human consumption and has the authority's approval is known as an abattoir. (SDS, 2016). The majority of the country's slaughterhouses is over 50 years old and lack basic amenities like appropriate flooring, water supply, ventilation, etc. Their situation is far from satisfactory right now. The recommendations are intended to assist in modernizing existing slaughterhouses and establishing new slaughterhouses with a focus on increased waste utilization. Codex, (1985). As a national scientific control agency, the Sudanese Standards and Metrology agency (SSMO) is mandated by one of its laws to develop national standards and adopt international standards through technical and specialized committees from governmental and non-governmental organizations in coordination with SSMO (SDS, 2016). In addition to the general requirements listed in the module "layout and construction," each particular meat trade has its own needs that improve the sanitary production of that particular sort of meat. Abattoirs are specifically designed so that the employees may kill and dress the carcass in a hygienic manner. They also

encourage simple working circumstances to prevent stressful working conditions, which will lead to undesired workplace behaviors. Gracey, (1981). Regulations have been issued to make sure that the building's layout will facilitate the simple handling of carcasses and that proper procedures are followed. The precise specifications required for a red meat abattoir, its cutting plants, and how the process of slaughter and dressing should be done to ensure a safe and hygienic product are all covered in this lesson. Gracey, (1981). The objective is to maintain good hygiene and sanitation in slaughter house and to minimize environmental problems of Gezira states. To assess standards and metrology of local slaughter houses of Gezira state. To evaluate the hygienic production of specific type of meat and to assess the local slaughter houses position compared to the Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO).

Material and Methods

Site of the Study

This study was carried out in Gezira state, South Khartoum Capital of Sudan (about 186km) and center of Gezira scheme. Gezira state poses more than 12 slaughterhouses such as: Alkaripa, WadAlhadad, Baracat, AlhajAballa, Almanagil, Almeheriba, Almadina Arab, Alhoush, ALbagair, Tamboul, and Roufaa.

Experimental Design and Grouping

A total of 12 local slaughterhouse of Gezira state from different sites of localities were divide into three categories of local slaughterhouse of Gezira state according to their constructions and establishment as following

1. Group (A)

Al Bagair slaughterhouse, Alkaripa slaughterhouse, Almanagil slaughterhouse and Roufaa slaughterhouse

2. Group (B)

Elkamlien slaughter house, Wad Alhadad slaughterhouse, AlHasahesa slaughterhouse and Baracat slaughterhouse

3. Group (C)

Al Meheriba slaughterhouse, Al Madena Arab slaughterhouse, Al Housh slaughterhouse, Haj Abdallah slaughterhouse.

Nature of the Study

The study depends on Sudanese standard specification 294/2016 and the Sudanese Standard Specification for the transportation and handling of meat products and slaughterhouses were evaluated according to Sudanese standard specification for slaughterhouses. Slaughterhouse evaluation to assess the conformity of slaughterhouses in terms through specific data sheets according to (SSMO, 2016) as the following:

Location of the slaughterhouse, Location of the slaughterhouse, Design of the buildings, Accessories and tools, Slaughter hall, Services and their attachments and General requirements for slaughterhouse work

Data Collection

Slaughterhouse data

Data sheets were created includes ten (10) items (1-10), each item score ten marks when SSMO was found actually for evaluating the flowing parameters:

Slaughterhouse site, the general shape, Building design, Accessories, Equipments, Drainage, Services and General requirements.

Statistical analysis

All the data of the experiments were statistically analyzed with Chi square test. by using the computer with Statistical Package for Social Study (SPSS) program and Duncan multiple range tests was used to detect difference between means (Snedecor and Cochran, 1980).

Result and Discussion

Slaughterhouse location shown in table 1 (Appendix). According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets the study showed no significant different ($P < 0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughterhouse site for living area, waste places,

industrial polluted areas, odorous areas, insect and pest areas, livestock marketing place, main roads and voltage areas and communication media while the study showed significant different ($P < 0.05$) between experimental groups for slaughter house height and drainage system. In Table (1), we note that each group contains four slaughterhouses, group 3 slaughterhouses that match the living area item and one slaughterhouse that do not match. In the waste place item, the matching percentage of the first group is 25 percent, due to the proximity of 3 slaughterhouses of the group to waste areas, as well as group B. As for group C, the matching percentage is zero in percent, due to the presence of the four slaughterhouses in waste areas, so waste placement must be prevented. Group B and C are 50 percent identical, as there are 2 slaughterhouses in each group in the waste dumping areas. Industrial pollution, the first group, the percentage of conformity is 50, because 2 of them are far from the pollution areas, while the group B and S are non-conforming, the percentage is 100 percent, due to the presence of all slaughterhouses in the areas of industrial pollution. All groups do not conform to the item of insects and pests due to the presence of all slaughterhouses in insect breeding areas. The location of the livestock markets, groups A and B, are 75 percent identical, as there are livestock markets close to them, except for a slaughterhouse in each group that does not match. The main roads and electricity meters of groups A, B, and C do not conform by 100 percent. This is due to the distance of the slaughterhouses from the main roads and the non-conformity of the electricity. Likewise, the means of communication are not identical in all groups, because they are not available in all slaughterhouses. The height of the slaughterhouse, the matching group, increased by 100 percent compared to the group. The matching rate was 75 percent, due to the non-matching of the height of one slaughterhouse. As for group C, it did not match, matching by 100 percent, because all slaughterhouses did not match the item of slaughterhouse height. As for the sanitation of the slaughterhouses of the first group, it is identical by 100 percent in 100, due

to the presence of sanitation in all the slaughterhouses of the group. As for the two groups, B and C, it is identical by 100 percent, because there is no sanitation in the slaughterhouses of the two groups.

Slaughterhouse general structure evaluation in table 2 (Appendix) According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets the study showed no significant different ($P < 0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughterhouse general structure for while the study showed significant different ($P < 0.05$) between experimental groups for slaughter house Workers entrance and exits, Animal entrance door Preparing, operations, Waiting pens. The fencing of the slaughterhouse in the group is 75% identical, due to the presence of one of the four non-conforming slaughterhouses in the Tsuirama, group B, which is 25% identical, to match one slaughterhouse. As for group C, it is not identical because there is no fencing in all the slaughterhouses. The entrances and exits of the workers in group A are 100% identical, due to the conformity of all slaughterhouses to this item, while group B and non-conformance are 100%, because all the slaughterhouses in the two groups do not conform to the item of entrances and exits for workers. The animal entrances in group A are 75% identical, due to the presence of three slaughterhouses that conform to the animal entrances item. As for the two groups, B and c, they are not 100% identical, because all the slaughterhouses of the two groups do not conform to the animal entrances item. The processing operations in the two groups A and B match the rate of 25%, because there is one slaughterhouse in each group, and the equipment item in group C is identical, with a rate of 50%, because there are two slaughterhouses in the group, where the equipment is identical. The waiting sheds in group A match 100%, while group B is the opposite, the matching percentage is zero, because there are no waiting sheds in all the group's slaughterhouses, but group C matches

by 100%, because there are waiting sheds for all the group's slaughterhouses.

In table 3 (Appendix) According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets the study showed no significant different ($P < 0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughterhouse structure design for Emergency slaughtering pens, Refused animal pens, Laboratory, Incinerator, Café tea area, Bath room, Waste Processing unit while the study showed significant different ($P < 0.05$) between experimental groups for slaughter house Fit animal pens, Slaughterhouse hall, Storage room. The healthy animal pens of group A are 100% identical, due to the presence of identical animal pens in all the slaughterhouses of the group, or group B, the matching rate is 25%, because there are matching pens in only one slaughterhouse. Group C is not 100% identical, because there are no animal pens in all the group's slaughterhouses. Emergency slaughtering pens. The first group conforms by 25%, due to the presence of only one slaughterhouse that contains this item. As for groups B and C, they do not conform by 100%, due to the fact that not all slaughterhouses contain the item of forced slaughter sheds. All groups A and B, all of them do not conform to the item of unfit animal pens, due to the fact that they are not found in all slaughterhouses. Slaughter hall, group A, the percentage of conformity is 50%, due to the presence of slaughter hall in Muslims, while groups B and group C are not identical by 100%, due to the absence of slaughter hall in all slaughterhouses. The first group has a matching rate of 25%, due to the presence of a library in one slaughterhouse, while groups B and group C are not 100% matched, due to the absence of a library in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A conforms by 75%, because it contains three slaughterhouses in which there are storage rooms. Group B and Group C are not 100% identical because there are no storage rooms in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. All ABS groups do not contain an incinerator, so they do not comply with the specification. The conformity rate for the first group is 50%, due to the presence of the item in

two slaughterhouses. As for group B and group C, the matching percentage is zero, due to the absence of a cafeteria. Group A is 50% identical, due to the presence of the item in two slaughterhouses, or group B and group C are not identical, i.e. the percentage of conformity is zero, because there are no bathrooms in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A conforms with a rate of 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse that conforms to this item. Group B and Group C are not identical, with a compliance rate of zero.

According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets, In table 4 (Appendix) the study showed no significant different ($P < 0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughterhouse for Maintenance workshop while the study showed significant different ($P < 0.05$) between experimental groups for slaughter house Car wash unit, Building foundation, Slaughterhouse walls, Slaughterhouse floor, Slaughterhouse roofs, Ventilation and light, Pens design, Animals Partitions, Water resources, Animal quarantine, Animal transport traffics. The matching percentage of groups is zero, due to the absence of car washes in all slaughterhouses. Group A conformity with a rate of 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse with a maintenance workshop, while Group A and Group B have a compliance rate of zero, due to the absence of maintenance workshops in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. The first group conforms to the Building foundation clause, due to the presence of building construction in all the slaughterhouses of the group. As for Group B and Group C, they do not conform to the Building Foundation clause because there are no buildings in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A is 100% identical in order to match the floors in all group slaughterhouses, or group B and group C are 25% identical in order to match one slaughterhouse in each group in the slaughterhouse walls item. Group A is 100% identical, in order to match the floors in all the slaughterhouses of group B and group C. They are not identical because the floors are not identical in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A is 100% identical, in order to

match the roofs in all the slaughterhouses of group B and group C. They are not identical because the roofs are not identical in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A is 100% identical, in order to match the in Ventilation and light the slaughterhouses of group B and group C. They are not identical because the Ventilation and light identical in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. All slaughterhouses of group B or group C conform to the pens design clause by 100% due to the presence of sheds in all slaughterhouses in all groups. Group A matches 100%, and that is the Animal partition in all the slaughterhouses of group A, while group B matches 25%, because there is one slaughterhouse in which there is an Animal partition. The first group matches with a percentage of 100 for the presence of a water source in all the slaughterhouses of the group. As for Group B and Group C, it does not match. It corresponds to zero percentage because there is no water source in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A matches 100% due to the presence of Animal quarantine in all group slaughterhouses, Group B matches 25% due to the presence of one slaughterhouse with Animal quarantine. Group C is non-compliant due to the absence of Animal quarantine in all group slaughterhouses. Group A conforms by 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse that conforms to the Animal quarantine clause, while Group B and Group C are not identical because there is no Animal transport in all slaughterhouses.

Slaughterhouse hall evaluation showed In table 5 (Appendix) According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets the study showed no significant different ($P < 0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughterhouse for Stunning area, Animals movement, Slaughterhouse halls, By-products halls, Carcass processing halls, Head and feet collecting room, Condemnation room, Carcass freezing unit, Cargo and upload unit, Balances while the study showed significant different ($P < 0.05$) between experimental groups for slaughter house Bleeding area, Drainage unit, Leather collection room, Carcass dissection halls. Group A matched by 75%, due to the

presence of three slaughterhouses that have a bleeding area, while group A and group C matched zero, due to the absence of a Bleeding area in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A is 75% conformity, due to the presence of three slaughterhouses, group B and group C, the percentage of conformity is zero, due to the absence of a drainage unit in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A, the matching rate is 50%, the percentage of matching animal movement in two slaughterhouses, while Group B and Group C, the matching rate is zero%, due to the lack of compliance with the item Animal movement in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A, the matching rate% 25 the percentage of matching of slaughterhouse in one slaughterhouse while Group B and Group C, the matching rate is zero%, due to the lack of compliance with the item slaughterhouse Hall in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A conforms to 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse that conforms to the Byproducts Hall item. Group B and Group C have zero conformity, due to the absence of a slaughterhouse in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A is 50% identical, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses with car Cass. Processing As for group A and group C, its conformity is zero%, due to the absence of this item in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A is 75% identical, due to the presence of three slaughterhouses containing a leather collection room, while Group B and Group C are inconsistent because there is no leather collection room item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A is 50% identical, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses with this item, or Group B and Group C, their conformity is zero%, due to the absence of Head and feet call in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A, its conformity rate is 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse that is identical to the condemnation room item, while group B and group C have zero compliance due to the absence of this item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A conforms to 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse that conforms to the item carcass freezing unite,

while Group B and Group C do not conform to the absence of this item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A is 75% identical to item carcasses dissection Halls. This is due to the presence of three slaughterhouses that are identical to this item, while group B and group C are not identical to this item, because there are no slaughterhouses containing carcass dissection halls in the two groups. Group A conforms to this item by 50%, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses conforming to this item, while Group B and Group C have zero conformity because this item is not found in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A corresponds to 50%, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses in which there is an item Balances, while groups B and Group C correspond to zero, due to the absence of Balance in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups.

According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets, In table 6 (Appendix) the study showed no significant different ($P < 0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughterhouse for Offices Management services, Workers services room, Light services, Temperature services, Equipment's and tools, Operation rooms, Maintenance workshop, Workers café tea area, Coming room while the study showed significant different ($P < 0.05$) between experimental groups for slaughter house Electricity. Group A has a 50% compliance rate, due to the presence of Offices Management services in two slaughterhouses, while Group B and Group C have a compliance rate of 0%, due to the lack of an Offices Management services item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A, the compliance rate is 50%, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses that have Offices Management services, while Group B and Group C have zero compliance, due to the absence of this item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A matches by 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse in which there is a workers services room, while Group B and Group X match it to zero, because there is no workers services room in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A

matches by 25%, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses, one of which has light services, while Group B and Group C match it to zero because there is no lighting in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A matches 50%, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses temperature services, while group B and group C match them zero, due to the lack of this item. Group A has 25% compliance, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse with equipment and tools, while Group B and Group C have zero compliance because this item is not available in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A matches by 25%, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses, one of which has light services, while Group B and Group C match it to zero because there is no lighting in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A corresponds to 50%, due to the presence of operation rooms in two slaughterhouses in group A, group B and group C, their conformity is zero, due to the absence of operation rooms in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A conforms to 25%, due to the presence of a slaughterhouse only that conforms to the maintenance work shop item, while Group B and Group C have zero compliance due to the absence of the Maintenance work shop item in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. All groups are matched to zero because there is no Workers Cafe tea area item in all slaughterhouses. The rest room of group A matches by 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse with a rest room, while group B and group C match them to zero because there is no rest room in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups.

The table 7 (Appendix) According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets the study showed no significant different ($P < 0.05$) among different slaughterhouse categories for slaughterhouse for Equipments and tools cleaning, Cleaning materials, Birds and insects displace, Pesticide conserved, Pesticide conserved, Workers training courses, Workers medical detection, Workers medical certificates, Workers behavior, Visitors clean cloth, Stamps, Workers cloth. Group A conforms to 25%, due to the presence of one slaughterhouse with

equipment and tools cleaning, while Group B and Group C have zero conformity, due to the lack of an item of equipment and tools cleaning in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A has 50% compliance due to the presence of cleaning material in two slaughterhouses in the group, while Group B and Group C have zero compliance due to the lack of a cleaning material item in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A conforms to 50%, due to the presence of two slaughterhouses in which there is an item “birds and insects displace.” As for group B and group C, it conforms to zero, due to the absence of an item “birds and insects displace” in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A has 25% compliance, due to the presence of an item pesticide conserved in one slaughterhouse in the group, while group B and group C have zero compliance, due to the absence of this item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. The group matched it 25%, due to the presence of an item Worker training courses in one of the group’s slaughterhouses, while Group B and Group C matched it zero, due to the absence of an item Worker training courses in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A corresponded to 25% due to the presence of the item Workers medical detection in one slaughterhouse, while Group B and Group C matched them to zero, due to the absence of the item Workers medical detection in all

slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A corresponds to 50%, due to the presence of Workers medical certification in two slaughterhouses, while Group B and Group C correspond to zero, due to the absence of Workers medical certification in all slaughterhouses of the two groups. The group matched it 25%, due to the presence of the Workers behavior item in one of the group’s slaughterhouses, while Group B and Group C matched it zero because there was no Workers behavior item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A has 75% compliance due to the presence of Visitor clean cloth in three slaughterhouses, while Group B has 25% compliance due to the presence of the Visitor clean cloth item in one slaughterhouse, and Group X has zero compliance due to the absence of the Visitor clean cloth item in all slaughterhouses of the group. Group A has 25% compliance due to the presence of the Stamps item in one slaughterhouse, while Group B and Group C have zero compliance due to the absence of the Stamps item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups. Group A has 25% compliance with the Workers cloth item in one slaughterhouse, while Group B and Group C have zero compliance due to the absence of the Workers cloth item in all the slaughterhouses of the two groups.

Table 8. Average Values (Mean+ EE) of Slaughtered Animals per Head/Year According to Localities

Localities	Beef	Sheep	Goats	Camel
Wad Madani	1989.43 ^a	786.13 ^b	78.88 ^c	4.15 ^c
Elkamleen	826.17 ^b	472.78 ^{cd}	280.08 ^a	.32 ^c
Elhasaheisa	1499.55 ^{cb}	543.03 ^c	142.52 ^b	.28 ^c
South Gezira	801.18 ^b	546.35 ^c	256.85 ^a	15.42 ^c
East Gezira	282.05 ^d	603.98 ^b	239.73 ^a	91.70 ^b
Elmanagil	651.70 ^c	781.58 ^b	158.37 ^b	165.43 ^a
Umelgura	637.10 ^c	381.60 ^d	67.55 ^c	9.25 ^c
Elghurashi	740.42 ^{bc}	1355.68 ^a	47.20 ^c	2.85 ^c
<i>SE</i>	53.50	74.23	17.04	5.94
<i>Sig</i>	**	**	**	**

In table (8) According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets the study showed the significant different (P<0.05)

between experimental Years of Slaughters for slaughter house animals per head according to localities.

In table (9) According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization sheets the study showed the significant different (P<0.05)

between experimental Years of Slaughters for slaughter house animals per head.

Table 9. Average Values (Mean+ EE) of Slaughtered Animals per Head According to a Year

Years of Slaughters	Beef	Sheep	Goats	Camel
2017	1034.75 ^a	656.13 ^a	165.76 ^a	37.17 ^a
2018	887.77 ^{bc}	783.28 ^a	157.12 ^{ab}	22.52 ^b
2019	838.49 ^c	490.87 ^b	169.10 ^a	39.10 ^a
2020	888.04 ^{bc}	692.30 ^a	171.08 ^a	42.79 ^a
2021	993.20 ^{ab}	796.96 ^a	131.43 ^b	39.29 ^a
<i>SE</i>	42.29	58.69	13.47	4.69
<i>Sig</i>	**	**	**	**

Conclusion

Categories of group A showed significant different (P<0.05) for slaughterhouse site, general structure, structures design, accessories, halls, access services and slaughterhouse general requirements.

According to slaughtered animals during the periods (2017 – 2021) Wad Madani locality tended to have superior values of slaughtered beef while Elghurashi locality scored the highest values for slaughtered sheep and (Elkamlean, South Gezira and East Gezira) reported the highest values of slaughtered goats. Elmanagil locality reported the highest values of slaughtered camels.

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Appendix

Table 1. Slaughterhouse Site Evaluation According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO) - Gezira Sudan

Slaughterhouses Categories Stander values%	A				B				C				Total				Chi	Sig
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Living areas	3	75	1	25	2	50	2	50	2	50	2	50	7	58.3	5	41.7	0.69	NO
Waste places	1	25	3	75	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	1.2	NO
Industrial polluted areas	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Odorous areas	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Insect and pest areas	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	12	100	0	NO
Livestock marketing place	3	75	1	25	3	75	1	25	4	100	0	0.0	10	83.3	2	16.7	1.2	NO
Main roads and voltage areas	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	12	100	0.0	0.0	0.00	NO
Communication media	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	12	100	0.0	0.0	0.00	NO
Slaughter house height	4	100	0.0	0.0	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	7	58.3	5	41.7	8.91	**
Drainage system	4	100	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	4	33.3	8	66.7	12	**

Table 2. Slaughterhouse General Structure Evaluation According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO) - Gezira Sudan

Slaughterhouses Categories Stander values%	A				B				C				Total				Chi	Sig
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Surround structure	3	75	1	25	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	4	33.3	8	66.7	5.25	NO
Workers entrance and exits	4	100	0.0	0.0	0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	4	33.3	8	66.7	12	**
Animal entrance door	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	3	25	9	75	8	**
Preparing operations	1	25	3	75	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	1.2	**
Waiting pens	4	100	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	4	33.3	8	66.7	12	**

Table 3 Slaughterhouse Structures Design Evaluation According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO) - Gezira Sudan

Slaughterhouses Categories Stander values%	A				B				C				Total				Chi	Sig
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Fit animal pens	4	100	0.0	0.0	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	5	41.75	7	58.25	8.91	**
Emergency slaughtering pens	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Refused animal pens	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	12	100	0.0	NO
Slaughterhouse hall	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	**
Laboratory	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Storage room	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	3	25	9	75	8	**
Incinerator	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	NO
Café tea area	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.7	4.8	NO
Bath room	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.7	4.8	NO
Waste Processing unit	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO

Table 4. Slaughterhouse Accessories Evaluation According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO) - Gezira Sudan

Slaughterhouses Categories Stander values%	A				B				C				Total				Chi	Sig
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Car wash unit	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	12	100	0.0	**
Maintenance workshop	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.10	NO
Building foundation	4	100	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	4	33.3	8	66.7	12.0	**
Slaughterhouse walls	4	100	0.0	0.0	1	25	3	75	1	25	3	75	5	41.7	7	58.3	8.9	**
Slaughterhouse floor	4	100	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	4	33.3	8	66.7	12.0	**
Slaughterhouse roofs	4	100	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00	4	100	0.0	0.0	0.00	4	4	33.3	8	66.7	12.0	**
Ventilation and light	4	100	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00	4	0.0	0.0	0.00	4	4	33.3	8	66.7	12.0	**
Pens design	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	33.3	8	66.7	12.0	**
Animals Partitions	4	100	0.0	0.0	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	5	41.7	7	58.3	8.91	**
Water resources	4	100	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	4	33.3	8	66.6	12.0	**
Animal quarantine	4	100	0.0	0.0	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	4	41.7	7	58.3	8.91	**

Table 5. Slaughterhouse Hall Evaluation According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO) - Gezira Sudan

Slaughterhouses Categories Stander values%	A				B				C				Total				Chi	Sig
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Stunning area	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Bleeding area	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	3	25	9	75	8.0	**
Drainage unit	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	3	25	9	75	8.0	**
Animals movement	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Slaughterhouse halls	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
By-products halls	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Carcass processing halls	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Leather collection room	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	3	25	9	75	8.8	**
Head and feet collecting room	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Condemnation room	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Carcass freezing unit	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Carcass dissection halls	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	3	25	9	75	8.0	**
Cargo and upload unit	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Balances	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO

Table 6. Slaughterhouse Access Services Evaluation According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO) - Gezira Sudan

Slaughterhouses Categories Stander values%	A				B				C				Total				Chi	Sig
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Offices Management services	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	No
Workers services room	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Light services	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	No
Temperature services	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	No
Equipments and tools	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Electricity	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	3	25	9	75	8.0	*
Operation rooms	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Maintenance workshop	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Workers café tea area	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	NO
Coming room	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO

Table 7. Slaughterhouse General Requirements Evaluation According to Sudanese Standards and Metrology Organization (SSMO) - Gezira Sudan

Slaughterhouses Categories Stander values%	A				B				C				Total				Chi	Sig
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		NO			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Equipments and tools cleaning	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Cleaning materials	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Birds and insects displace	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Pesticide conserved	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Workers training courses	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Workers medical detection	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Workers medical certificates	2	50	2	50	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	2	16.7	10	83.3	4.8	NO
Workers behavior	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Visitors clean cloth	3	75	1	25	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	25	3	75	4	33.3	8	66.7	5.25	NO
Stamps	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO
Workers cloth	1	25	3	75	0.0	0.0	4	100	0.0	0.0	4	100	1	8.3	11	91.7	2.18	NO